

A dimensionless rheology-based extrusion map as a predictive tool for hot-melt extrusion processability

Dan Trunov^{*}, Lukáš Berčík, Samuel Křiška, Albert Behner, Miroslav Šoós^{**}

Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Chemistry and Technology, Technická 3, Dejvice, Prague 6, 166 28, Czech Republic

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ABSTRACT

Predicting the processability of polymeric materials in hot-melt extrusion remains a critical challenge in continuous manufacturing due to the complex transition from powder feeding to melt flow under dynamic processing conditions. In this work, we present a unified and predictive methodology for construction an extrusion processability map based on dimensionless rheological criteria. The framework first assesses powder feeding behavior using solid-state indicators, including the flowability index (ff_c), friction ratio (FR), and Froude number (Fr_d), to characterize feed consistency and uniformity. The analysis is subsequently extended to the melt-processing stage in a twin-screw extruder, where extrudability is described using dimensionless numbers that capture viscous, elastic, and inertial effects, namely the Bingham (Bn), Deborah (De), Weissenberg (Wi), and Reynolds (Re) numbers, along with the die swell (B) parameter. These criteria are integrated into a first-order predictive model that enables identification of stable extrusion processing windows. The resulting processability map provides mechanistic insight into the behavior of polymeric systems under defined operating conditions, reducing reliance on empirical trial-and-error approaches. Early identification of processing limitations supports efficient process optimization, leading to reduced material waste, lower energy consumption, and a smaller environmental footprint. While demonstrated using pharmaceutical polymer systems, the proposed methodology is broadly applicable to extrusion-based manufacturing across materials and chemical engineering.

1. Introduction

Hot-melt extrusion (HME) is a well-established industrial manufacturing technique, first introduced in the early 20th century [1]. The process involves transforming raw materials into products of uniform shape by forcing them through a die under elevated temperature and pressure conditions. A typical extruder consists of three principal sections [2]: *i*) the feeding system, responsible for delivering raw materials into the barrel, *ii*) the conveying and mixing section, where Archimedean screws transport and homogenize the material, and *iii*) the die assembly, which imparts the final shape to the extrudate. The geometry of the die and the operating parameters critically influence the shape and quality of the extruded product. Since its inception, HME has found widespread application across various industries, including plastics [3], polymer processing [4], food manufacturing [5], and more recently, pharmaceutical production [6].

Despite its industrial maturity and well-established principles, the complex multiphase, non-Newtonian flow behavior inherent to twin-

screw extrusion poses significant challenges for predictive modeling and process optimization. Each extrusion run involves numerous inter-dependent process parameters that must be optimized for specific formulations [7]. Optimization strategies commonly include: *i*) empirical trial-and-error approaches, *ii*) numerical simulations such as one-dimensional screw models, and *iii*) predictive flow behavior analysis through microscale or physicochemical screening techniques.

The empirical approach remains the dominant strategy due to its robustness and regulatory acceptance. However, operational constraints, such as allowable temperature, feed rate, and screw speed, must be strictly observed to maintain continuous flow and prevent material stagnation within the barrel. Design of experiments (DoE) [8] methodologies offer a structured alternative by systematically investigating factor-response relationships. However, a full-factorial DoE for twin-screw extrusion encompassing seven factors (five temperature in five zones along the extruder length, feed rate, and screw speed) which could require up to 2187 (3^7) experimental runs. Fractional factorial designs, such as the Box–Behnken design [9], reduce this to fewer than 100 runs per material, due to the implication of three-level contributions

^{*} Corresponding author.

^{**} Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: dan.trunov@vscht.cz (D. Trunov), miroslav.soos@vscht.cz (M. Šoós).

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Nomenclature	
A_{EXT}	Cross-sectional area of the extruder, m^2
A_{FED}	Cross-sectional area of the feeder, m^2
a_T	Horizontal shift factor, $\exp\left(\frac{-C_1(T-T_{ref})}{C_2+(T-T_{ref})}\right)$ (Eq. (6))
b_T	Vertical shift factor, $G'(\omega, T)/G'(a_T\omega, T_{ref})$ (Eq. (7))
B	Die swell parameter, $k\sigma_n/\tau_m$ (Eq. (21))
Bn	Bingham number, $\tau_p H/(\eta^* v_{EXT})$ (Eq. (17))
$C_1; C_2$	Empirical constants for the polymer system, -
C_I	Carr compressibility index, $100^*(V_0 - V_B)/V_0$ (Eq. (4))
D_{EXT}	Characteristic length of twin-screw extruder, m
D_{FED}	Characteristic length of twin-screw feeder, m
De	Deborah number, λ/t_{pro} (Eq. (18))
E_A	Activation energy, J
FR	Friction ratio, $\tan(\varphi_i)/\tan(\varphi_w)$ (Eq. (3))
Frd	Froude number, $v_{FED}/\sqrt{\beta g H}$ (Eq. (16))
ff_c	Flowability index, $\sigma_{MPS}/\sigma_{UYS}$ (Eq. (1))
G'	Storage modulus, Pa
G''	Loss modulus, Pa
g	Gravitational acceleration constant, $m\ s^{-2}$
H	Distance between shaft and flight, m
$H(\lambda)$	Relaxation time spectrum, Pa
k	Specific parameter of die geometry and material, -
k_B	Boltzmann constant, $J\ K^{-1}$
M	Fragile index, $\partial(\log \eta^*)/\partial(T_g/T) _{T=T_g}$ (Eq. (22))
\dot{m}	Mass flow rate, $kg\ s^{-1}$
n	Screw rotation speed, RPM
P	Length of pitch per rotation, m
Q_{screw}	Theoretical maximum flow rate of the material, $kg\ s^{-1}$
r	Screw shaft radius, m
R	Screw flight radius, m
Re	Reynold number, $\rho_B v_{EXT} H/\eta^*$ (Eq. (20))
R_f	Flow resistance factor, $1/(1+\mu 2R/H)$ (Eq. (13))
SME	Specific mechanical energy, $J\ kg^{-1}$ (Eq. (15))
T	Temperature, K
T_g	Glass transition temperature, K
T_M	Melting temperature, K
T_{ref}	Reference temperature, K
t_{MRT}	Median residence time in the extruder, s
t_{pro}	Characteristic process time, s
V	Volume of the extruder, m^3
V_0	Apparent volume of powder specified at 0.01 kPa of consolidation stress, m^3
V_B	Apparent volume of powder, m^3
v_{EXT}	Flow velocity of the extruder, $m\ s^{-1}$
v_{FED}	Flow velocity of the feeder, $m\ s^{-1}$
W	Channel width, m
Wi	Weissenberg number, $\lambda\dot{\gamma}$ (Eq. (19))
$\dot{\gamma}$	Shear rate of the extruder, s^{-1}
γ	Shear strain, s^{-1}
$\tan \delta$	Loss factor or damping factor, $\tan \delta = G''/G'$ (Eq. (5))
δ	Phase angle shift, $^\circ$
η^*	Complex dynamic viscosity, $Pa\ s$ $ \eta^* = \sqrt{(\eta'')^2 + (\eta')^2}$
λ	Relaxation time, s
λ_{max}	Longest relaxation time of the material, s
μ	Wall friction factor, τ_w/σ_w (Eq. (2))
ρ_0	Bulk density specified at 0.01 kPa of consolidation stress, $kg\ m^{-3}$
ρ_B	Bulk density, $kg\ m^{-3}$
ρ_M	Melt density, $kg\ m^{-3}$
σ_{MPS}	Major Principal Stress, Pa
σ_{UYS}	Unconfined Yield Strength, Pa
σ_n	Normal stress of the material, Pa
σ_w	Wall normal stress, Pa
T_0	Torque, $kg\ m^2\ s^{-2}$
τ	Shear stress, Pa
τ_c	Cohesion of the powder, Pa
τ_m	Melt shear stress, Pa
τ_p	Powder shear stress, Pa
τ_w	Wall shear stress, Pa
φ_i	Angle of internal friction, deg
φ_w	Wall friction angle, deg
ω	Angular velocity, rad/s

center points. While feasible for experienced operators, these experiments entail considerable material usage, environmental impact, and energy consumption.

Numerical simulations present a cost-effective approach for predicting optimal extrusion parameters, thus reducing material and energy requirements. Accurate simulations demand robust initial conditions, often derived from theoretical calculations or physicochemical characterization. Experimental screening methods such as differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) [10], melt rheology [11], and hot-stage microscopy [12] elucidate key thermal transitions (e.g., glass transition temperature) and miscibility in polymer blends. Complementary theoretical approaches, including molecular modeling [13] and solubility parameter estimation [14], further inform about the system's behavior. These data feed into computational fluid dynamics (CFD) models that predict temperature distribution [15], residence time [16], and flow profiles [17] within the screw configuration [18]. However, such simulations are computationally intensive, sometimes requiring days to months for a single material system [19].

Melt rheology, particularly in plate-plate (PP) geometry, provides critical parameters such as temperature-dependent viscosity [20] and glass transition temperature [21]. These properties enable torque requirement predictions and combined with powder rheology, yield insights into feedstock flowability [22]. Nevertheless, rheological measurements alone cannot fully capture complex material behavior in

critical extruder regions, such as mixing zones or the die, where viscoelastic or elastoplastic flow dominates. Insufficient softening in these zones may cause screw blockage, manifesting as abrupt torque spikes.

Recent advancements in process analytical technology (PAT) [23, 24], including in-line Raman spectroscopy [25], near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy [26], and torque/pressure sensors, have enhanced real-time monitoring and control of HME processes. However, such techniques often require specialized instrumentation and calibration, limiting their applicability during early-stage development, or with highly viscous or opaque materials. Thus, there remains a need for predictive tools that are experimentally accessible, material-specific, and capable of delineating processability without the necessity for full-scale extrusion trials.

The objective of the present study is to develop a predictive methodology for assessing HME processability using only offline rheological measurements, thereby providing an experimentally accessible and material-efficient tool for early-stage formulation development. To achieve this, we introduce a DoE-based framework built on dimensionless physicochemical criteria that quantitatively describe material behavior within distinct extruder barrel zones. These criteria allow the identification of stable processing window and the detection of regions prone to flow instabilities, screw blockage, or oscillatory flow. The novelty of this work lies in the integration of standard rheological measurements into a zone-specific, dimensionless processability model

that directly connects material properties to extrusion performance. In contrast to previously reported approaches that rely heavily on extensive experimental extrusion trials, advanced process analytical technologies, or computationally intensive simulations, our methodology enables the construction of extrusion maps using only readily accessible laboratory data, offering a low-cost, and resource efficient tool for continuous manufacturing. To demonstrate the applicability and robustness of this approach, we first applied it to the pure polymer Kollidon® VA 64 and then extended it to multicomponent systems containing four active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) [27]. This allowed us to evaluate the influence of formulation complexity on rheological behavior, processability, and reproducibility, highlighting the framework's potential for guiding formulation optimization and scale-up in HME. Overall, the proposed methodology provides a unified, predictive, and experimentally grounded alternative to conventional trial-and-error or computationally demanding approaches, while retaining the flexibility needed for early-stage screening and process design.

2. Experimental part

2.1. Materials and reagents

To predict extrusion parameters, a base polymer commonly used in pharmaceutical extrusion as an adhesive and medium-flowing powder was selected Kollidon® VA 64 coarse (BASF, Germany). The polymer exhibits an average particle size of $40 \pm 30 \mu\text{m}$. To modify the physicochemical properties of the polymer, various concentrations of APIs were incorporated into the final mixture. Rivaroxaban (RIV, $17 \pm 7 \mu\text{m}$) was used as one API and was kindly provided by Zentiva, k.s. (Prague, Czech Republic). Additionally, cannabinoid-based APIs, cannabidiol (CBD, $9 \pm 8 \mu\text{m}$), cannabigerol (CBG, $15 \pm 13 \mu\text{m}$), and cannabiol (CBN, $14 \pm 10 \mu\text{m}$) were obtained from Pharma Hemp (Slovenia). All raw materials and their physical mixtures were stored in a refrigerator at 4°C under constant relative humidity of 25 % to ensure reproducibility of the measurements.

2.2. Powder rheology

All rheological properties were measured using the MCR 702e MultiDrive rheometer (Anton Paar, Austria). For powder property measurements, the MultiDrive unit was equipped with a powder shear cell (PSC) setup, consisting of a mounting plate for the lower measurement shaft (see [Supplementary Information Figure SI 1](#)) and the L-PSC lower shaft for the PSC (see [Supplementary Information Figure SI 1](#)). All measurements were conducted at room temperature ($23 \pm 0.6^\circ\text{C}$) and repeated in triplicate to ensure reproducibility.

2.2.1. Uniaxial compression (Shear cell) measurement

The standard shear cell procedure was applied, consisting of three consecutive steps: *i*) compaction of the material using a consolidation bench, *ii*) preshearing of the powder under steady-state flow conditions, and *iii*) shearing until the powder yields. Prior to analysis, a preparation and time consolidation bench (see [Supplementary Information Figure SI 1](#)) was used. The material was compacted by applying normal stresses equal to 33% (i.e. 1 kPa) of the initial target consolidation stress (3 kPa), based on the weight-specific consolidation stress of the PSC32 cell (see [Supplementary Information Figure SI 1](#)), inside the C-PSC32 shear cell cup (see [Supplementary Information Figure SI 1](#)).

Uniaxial compression measurements were performed at four initial consolidation stress (preshear) values: 3 kPa, 6 kPa, 9 kPa, and 12 kPa. The shearing cycle was measured under three different normal stress values corresponding to initial preshear levels of 30%, 55%, and 80% of the consolidation stress. During measurements, the shear cell probe PSC32-21-9 (see [Supplementary Information Figure SI 1](#)) was continuously rotated at a speed of 0.005 min^{-1} to determine the shear-to-failure

stress [28]. The outcome of this process is the yield locus, as shown in [Supplementary Information Figure SI 2](#). The flowability index (Eq. (1)) was determined from each corresponding yield locus, and the average value was subsequently calculated.

The yield locus represents the relationship between the measured shear-to-failure stress and the applied normal stress, typically fitted by a best-fit line. The intercept of this line on the shear stress axis (y-axis) corresponds to the shear stress at zero normal stress, reflecting the cohesion of the powder (τ_c). The angle between the best-fit line and the x-axis represents the angle of internal friction (φ_i).

To determine the Unconfined Yield Strength (σ_{UYS}) and Major Principal Stress (σ_{MPS}), the Mohr stress circle is applied. This circle provides a geometric representation of the stresses acting on various planes within the bulk powder. One Mohr circle passes through the origin and is tangent to the yield locus. This represents the conditions of critical to failure. A second Mohr circle is tangent to the yield locus and passes through the preshear point (steady-state flow), representing the critical state. From the Mohr circles, it is possible to extract valuable information about the powder's flow properties, which are expressed quantitatively as the ff_c [29,30]:

$$ff_c = \frac{\sigma_{MPS}}{\sigma_{UYS}} \quad (1)$$

2.2.2. Kinematic wall friction (Jenike shear) measurement

Kinematic wall friction measurement characterizes the frictional interaction between a bulk solid and a solid surface. The solid surface was selected based on the material properties used in the HME procedure. It is a stainless-steel friction disc with a maximum surface roughness of $0.25 \mu\text{m}$. The experimental setup is conceptually similar to the uniaxial compression test and comprises two main steps: *i*) consolidation of the bulk material and *ii*) measurement of wall shear stress. Material preparation was performed using the same consolidation bench as in shear cell tests (Section 2.2.1). However, for wall friction measurements, the material was compacted by applying a normal stress equal to 40% (i.e. 6 kPa) of the intended wall normal stress (σ_w). This was based on the weight-specific consolidation stress of the PSC42 cell (see [Supplementary Information Figure SI 1](#)), with the bulk sample loaded into the C-PSC42 shear cell cup (see [Supplementary Information Figure SI 1](#)). During measurement, the bulk specimen was sheared across the surface of the wall material using the PSC43-21-0 shear cell probe (stainless steel disc; [Supplementary Information Figure SI 1](#)) at a constant shear velocity of 0.05 min^{-1} [28]. This procedure, referred to as wall shear measurement, was carried out under four different initial wall normal stresses: 12 kPa, 9 kPa, 6 kPa, and 3 kPa. The wall shear stress (τ_w) was continuously recorded until it reached a steady-state value, indicating the establishment of kinematic equilibrium between the bulk solid and the wall surface. The result of this procedure is the wall yield locus, shown in [Supplementary Information Figure SI 3](#).

The wall yield locus describes the relationship between the wall normal stress and the corresponding steady-state wall shear stress. It quantifies the kinematic wall friction, representing the shear stress required to induce relative movement of the bulk material against the wall under various normal loads. When the wall yield locus is approximated with a linear fit extrapolated to zero normal stress, the slope of the best-fit line defines the angle of wall friction (φ_w), an indicator of wall frictional resistance. To further quantify wall friction behavior, the wall friction factor (μ), defined as the ratio of wall shear stress to wall normal stress at any point along the wall yield locus [31] can be calculated:

$$\mu = \frac{\tau_w}{\sigma_w} \quad (2)$$

Both parameters, the angle of wall friction and the wall friction factor, provide insight into the flow behavior of powders in contact with process equipment surfaces.

The relationship between the internal and wall friction characteristics of the bulk material was quantified using two key parameters: the internal friction angle (φ_i), representing the material's intrinsic resistance to shear deformation within the bulk, and the wall friction angle (φ_w), describing the resistance to motion at the interface between the bulk material and the contact surface. The combined effect of these parameters is expressed by a dimensionless quantity known as the friction ratio (FR), defined as the ratio of the internal to wall friction angles [32]:

$$FR = \frac{\tan(\varphi_i)}{\tan(\varphi_w)} \quad (3)$$

2.2.3. Carr compressibility index (Solid bulk density)

The degree of compressibility is determined by measuring the increase in bulk density with rising consolidation (normal) stress (see [Supplementary Information Figure SI 4](#)). Preparation of the material was identical to the procedure described in Section 2.2.1. The measurements were performed at a constant normal velocity of 50 mm s^{-1} , while a vertical force was applied through a flat probe of known area, corresponding to consolidation stresses ranging from 0 up to 45 kPa. From the specimen's height and mass under each load, the bulk density was calculated. Using the compressibility test, the bulk density under low consolidation normal stress specified at 0.01 kPa (ρ_0) was extracted. It represents the initial minimum value in the measurement process, and corresponds to the initial packing state of the material. Please note, that this value should not be confused with the tapped density determined by mechanical tapping methods. Second density extracted from compressibility test is bulk solid density under maximum value consolidation normal stress specified at 45 kPa (ρ_B) of the material. From these two densities, the Carr compressibility index (C_I) can be approximated as follows [31]:

$$C_I = \frac{V_0 - V_{B^*}}{V_0} 100 \% \quad (4)$$

where $V_0 = m/\rho_0$ is the apparent volume of powder specified at 0.01 kPa of consolidation stress, and $V_B = m/\rho_B$ is the apparent volume of powder specified at maximum normal stress (in our case 45 kPa). A compressibility index of zero indicates excellent flowability [33] or an essentially incompressible bulk solid.

2.3. Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA)

The same rheometer was used for the determination of dynamic mechanical properties of the material. However, instead of the PSC setup, the multidrive unit was equipped with a PP probe. The lower assembly was replaced with the Peltier temperature devices (P-PTD) 220 unit (see [Supplementary Information Figure SI 1](#)), while the upper part was equipped with the H-PTD 220 (see [Supplementary Information Figure SI 1](#)). The lower measurement plate consisted of a hard anodized aluminum plate (S-LP25/AL/G1; 25 mm; [Supplementary Information Figure SI 1](#)). The upper measurement plate (PP25; 25 mm) was made of stainless steel (see [Supplementary Information Figure SI 1](#)). All measurements are repeated in triplicate to ensure reproducibility.

The samples were prepared by compressing uniform powder using a custom-made 3D-printed cylindrical press (see [Supplementary Information Figure SI 5](#)). This setup consists of three components: *i*) left and *ii*) right bottom plates, which retain the powder and prevent free collapse, and *iii*) a piston used to compress the material into a tablet shape on the rheometer's bottom plate with a diameter of 25 mm. Powder was added until the compressed tablet (approx. 10 N) reached a final height of 2 mm. This prepared tablet served as the initial state of the material for two different types of rheological tests: *i*) dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA) and *ii*) dynamic oscillation.

In oscillatory rheological testing, a PP geometry is commonly used, in which the bottom plate remains stationary while the upper plate

performs rotational oscillations over a defined shear area under an applied shear force. The rotation of the upper plate induces shear deformation in the sample positioned between the two plates, which is described in terms of displacement (deflection path) and angular deflection. During testing, the sample is exposed to a controlled sinusoidal strain ($\gamma(t) = \gamma_0 \sin(\omega t)$). If the material behaves as an ideal elastic solid, there is no time lag between the applied strain and the resulting stress ($\tau(t) = \tau_0 \sin(\omega t + \delta)$) response, and the phase angle shift (δ) is zero degrees. Conversely, in an ideal viscous fluid (in our case under elevated temperature), the stress response lags behind the strain by a phase angle of 90° . For viscoelastic materials, the phase angle lies between 0 and 90° , indicating a combination of elastic and viscous behavior. To characterize such viscoelastic behavior, two fundamental parameters are measured: *i*) the storage modulus ($G' = \tau_0/\gamma_0 \cos \delta$) and *ii*) the loss modulus ($G'' = \tau_0/\gamma_0 \sin \delta$). The storage modulus G' reflects the elastic, energy-storing component, indicating how much energy the material can recover after deformation, while the loss modulus G'' represents the viscous, energy-dissipating component, describing the material's flow and energy loss as heat. By applying a controlled oscillatory deformation and measuring the resulting stress, these moduli provide intrinsic, material-specific data on both elastic and viscous properties [34,35].

2.3.1. DMTA measurement (Temperature sweep oscillation)

This type of measurement reveals the temperature-dependent behavior of the sample, enabling the assessment of physical properties and potential structural modifications. From these measurements, it is possible to extract the glass transition temperature (T_g), melting temperature (T_M), and relevant complex dynamic viscosity parameter of the analyzed material. The oscillatory temperature sweep was performed within the linear viscoelastic region (LVR), corresponding to an oscillation strain of 1 %, which equates to a plate deformation of 0.25 mm per rotation. The angular frequency (ω) was fixed at a constant value of 6.28 rad/s. The temperature range was set from 60°C to 160°C , with a heating/cooling ramp rate of $2^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ for the material Kollidon VA 64. In this type of experiment, the samples were heated from low to high temperatures and subsequently cooled in the opposite direction. During the measurement procedure, the sample was equilibrated at the boundary temperatures of 60°C and 160°C for 5 min. The instrument drive was configured to adjust the gap position while maintaining a constant normal force of 5 N, with a movement speed of $25 \mu\text{m}/\text{s}$. The glass transition and melting temperatures were determined as the crossover points between the loss modulus (G'') and the storage modulus (G'). This inflection point can also be identified using the loss factor or damping factor ($\tan \delta$), and can be expressed as [34]:

$$\tan \delta = \frac{G''}{G'} \quad (5)$$

2.3.2. Dynamic oscillation measurement (Frequency sweep)

This measurement is used to investigate the time-dependent deformation behavior of materials, as frequency is the inverse of time. It is important to note that this phenomenon can only be observed within the elastic, viscoelastic or viscous regime. From this type of analysis, the relaxation time (λ) and the relaxation time spectrum ($H(\lambda)$) of the polymer can be determined by fitting the experimental data to a generalized Maxwell model consisting of multiple Maxwell elements. In addition to time-related properties, the measurement of both storage modulus and loss modulus enables the calculation of the material's complex viscosity as a function of applied angular frequency. The complex viscosity was studied at various temperatures ranging from 100°C to 160°C , in 10°C intervals. The oscillation frequency was logarithmically decreased from 628 to $0.00628 \text{ rad}/\text{s}$, while maintaining a constant oscillation strain of 1%. The instrument drive was configured to adjust the gap position while maintaining a constant normal force of 5 N, with a movement speed of $25 \mu\text{m}/\text{s}$.

The outcome of this measurement is a set of data describing both storage and loss moduli as a function of angular frequency across a range of temperatures. From these data, a master curve of the storage modulus is constructed by combining several individual isothermal measurements, each performed at a different temperature. The master curve is generated using the Williams-Landel-Ferry (WLF) equation [36], which shifts the individual curves along the frequency axis (horizontal shift factor, a_T) and along the modulus axis (vertical shift factor, b_T), relative to a chosen reference temperature, here set at 130 °C. The selected temperature corresponds to the softening behavior of the polymer Kollidon VA64 and lies slightly below its melting point. This process produces a single continuous curve that represents the material's viscoelastic behavior over a broad timescale, including time or frequency ranges that cannot be directly accessed in a single measurement. The horizontal shift factor is calculated according to the following relations:

$$\log(a_T) = \frac{-C_1(T - T_{ref})}{C_2 + (T - T_{ref})} \quad (6)$$

where a_T is the horizontal shift factor, T is the measurement temperature, T_{ref} is the reference temperature, and C_1 and C_2 are empirical constants for the polymer system. The vertical shift factor (b_T) can be determined from:

$$G'(\omega, T) = b_T G'(a_T \omega, T_{ref}) \quad (7)$$

This time-temperature superposition principle allows prediction of the material's behavior over timescales extending far beyond those directly measurable in the experiment.

Viscoelastic materials exhibit both viscous and elastic behavior simultaneously. The viscous component follows Newton's law of viscosity, while the elastic component follows Hooke's law of elasticity. This dual behavior can be modeled using a combination of a spring (elastic element) and a dashpot (viscous element) arranged in parallel or series, depending on the specific viscoelastic model. One common approach is the Maxwell model [37], which uses a spring and a dashpot connected in series to describe time-dependent deformation. Viscoelastic deformation can be divided into three stages: *i*) initial loading, where no stress is applied and no deformation occurs; *ii*) loading under stress, where the spring deforms immediately and the dashpot deforms gradually over time, reflecting delayed viscous response; *iii*) unloading, where the spring returns to its original position, but the dashpot retains its deformation, resulting in irreversible strain. This irreversible response is characteristic of viscoelastic liquids. Because this behavior is complex and depends on time, its analysis involves solving an inverse mathematical problem, direct prediction from raw rheological data is generally not feasible. To address this, the viscoelastic response is often described using a generalized Maxwell model, which consists of multiple Maxwell elements (spring and dashpot pairs) arranged in parallel. Each element represents a polymer segment with a characteristic relaxation time (λ) [38]. The set of relaxation times and strengths motivates the representation of viscoelasticity as a continuous relaxation spectrum ($H(\lambda)$) [39], which represents the distribution of relaxation strengths as a function of relaxation time, ranging from near zero to a maximum relaxation time (λ_{max}) value defined by the material's structural limits. The total viscoelastic behavior is a superposition of these individual contributions and can be a set of discrete relaxation times and strengths, which can be written in a continuous form by the following equations for the storage modulus and loss modulus [40,41]:

$$G'(\omega) = \int_0^{\lambda_{max}} H(\lambda) \frac{\omega^2 \lambda^2}{1 + \omega^2 \lambda^2} \frac{d\lambda}{\lambda} \quad (8)$$

$$G''(\omega) = \int_0^{\lambda_{max}} H(\lambda) \frac{\omega \lambda}{1 + \omega^2 \lambda^2} \frac{d\lambda}{\lambda} \quad (9)$$

2.4. Preparation of solid dispersions using twin screw HME

A Pharma 11 twin-screw extruder (Thermo Fisher Scientific™, Karlsruhe, Germany) equipped with a gravimetric MiniTwin feeder (Brabender Technologie, Duisburg, Germany) was used to prepare extrudates from all mixtures and pure materials. The extruder screw has a diameter of 11 mm and a length-to-diameter (L/D) ratio of 40. The barrel is divided into seven temperature-controlled zones, each with an L/D of 5, in addition to a feeding zone maintained at a temperature approximately equal to that of the external circulation unit, and a die exit zone. The die has a diameter of 2 mm. The screw configuration selected corresponds to the standard geometry, as shown in [Supplementary Information Figure SI 6](#). Briefly, the screw consists of 33 conveying elements, two mixing zones equipped with kneading blocks comprising 12 and 10 elements, respectively, arranged at offset angles of 0°, 30°, 60°, and 90°, and a discharge element. To successfully extrude the selected material, three key parameters must be properly controlled: the feed rate, the screw rotation speed (n), and the temperature profile across the barrel zones.

2.4.1. Volumetric feeder

The feed rate was controlled using a MiniTwin feeder. For each individual material mixture, a separate calibration curve was prepared to correlate the volumetric feed rate with the mass flow rate (\dot{m}) of the material (see example in [Supplementary Information Figure SI 7](#)). The mass flow rate was converted to the flow velocity (v_{FED}) using the following equation:

$$v_{FED} = \frac{\dot{m}}{\rho_B A_{FED}} \quad (10)$$

where ρ_B is the bulk density of the material determined from powder rheology, and A_{FED} is the cross-sectional area of the feeder conveyer, which is a measured parameter. Please note that the temperature inside the volumetric feeder is equal to the ambient temperature.

2.4.2. Twin screw extrusion

In the barrel, two key parameters to be considered are, the screw rotation speed (n) and the temperature profile. While both parameters are described in detail in the following sections, a few simplifications were considered in this work. Let us assume that the total length of the mixing zones (L/D = 5) is much shorter than that of the conveying zones (L/D = 35). Under this condition, the overall shear rate ($\dot{\gamma}$) in the extruder can be approximated solely based on the geometry of the conveying elements (see full geometry in [Supplementary Information Figure SI 8](#)) using the mean logarithmic value, as follows [42]:

$$\dot{\gamma} = 8\pi \frac{n}{60} \ln \frac{R}{r} \frac{(R \cdot r)^2}{(R^2 - r^2)^2} \quad (11)$$

where R is the screw flight radius, and r is the screw shaft radius. In the situation where the screw speed is an independent parameter, the maximum throughput that the screw can handle is correlated with the maximum feed rate. Assuming that the barrel is open to the atmosphere and there are no volumetric limitations, the theoretical maximum volumetric flow rate (Q_{screw}) at a given screw speed can be calculated as [43]:

$$Q_{screw} = R_f \rho_b H W P n \quad (12)$$

where R_f is the flow resistance factor, W is the channel width, P is the pitch length per screw revolution, and H is the distance between shaft and flight. The flow resistance factor depends on powder rheology and is inversely proportional to the wall friction coefficient (μ) [44]. It can be derived from the traditional screw efficiency equation as a simplified, linearized expression [44]:

$$R_f = \frac{1}{1 + \mu \frac{2R}{H}} \quad (13)$$

Assuming the barrel is fully loaded and the flow is in steady state, the velocity through the extruder (v_{EXT}) can be expressed as:

$$v_{EXT} = \frac{V}{A_{EXT} t_{MRT}} \quad (14)$$

where V is the volume of the extruder, A_{EXT} is the cross-sectional area of the extruder conveyor, and t_{MRT} is the median residence time in the extruder (see [Supplementary Information Figure SI 9](#)). A key measurable output parameter in the extrusion process is the torque (T_0). From this, the specific mechanical energy (SME), a critical metric for evaluating the extrudability of a given formulation, can be calculated as follows:

$$SME = \frac{2\pi n T_0}{\dot{m}} \quad (15)$$

3. Results

3.1. Dimensionless criteria inside the feeder

The polymer processing sequence begins at the feeder, where the bulk powder material is introduced into the barrel of the extruder. Within the feeder, twin screws equipped with conveying elements facilitate material mixing, compression, and transport. While the material remains in the powder state, understanding its physicochemical properties is essential for characterizing adhesion and cohesion behavior. The powder state of the material can be described using three dimensionless parameters: ff_c , FR , and Froude number (Frd).

3.1.1. Powder state

The ff_c and FR provide complementary insights into the powder behavior of Kollidon VA 64 under different consolidation stresses. The ff_c indicates prone of the material to flow, with values above 10 corresponding to free-flowing powders, values of 4–10 representing easy-flowing, 2–4 as cohesive, and 1–2 as very cohesive [45]. As shown in [Fig. 1](#), pure Kollidon VA 64 exhibits excellent flow properties, with an average ff_c of approximately 15 (represented by the black dashed line), classifying it as a free-flowing material. Measurements at four different consolidation stresses reveal that lower stresses slightly increase the ff_c above the average, while higher stresses reduce flowability, indicating the material becomes stickier under compression.

Fig. 1. ff_c and FR of the polymer Kollidon VA 64 were determined under four different consolidation stresses. Lines represent the average value calculated from four independent measurements at each consolidation stress. The black dashed line and blue dashed line correspond to the ff_c and FR , respectively.

The FR provides additional information on the relative contributions of bulk cohesion and wall friction to powder transport, where two scenarios can be distinguished. When FR is below 1, wall friction dominates over internal cohesion, facilitating transport but potentially causing adhesion to the equipment walls. When FR is above 1, internal friction dominates, leading to resistance, blockages, or cohesive agglomeration [46,47]. For Kollidon VA 64, the average FR under the four consolidation stresses is approximately 0.78 (blue dashed line, right y-axis in [Fig. 1](#)). A slight increase in FR with higher consolidation stresses reflects increasing adhesive forces and reduced flowability. Nevertheless, FR remains below 1, indicating that wall friction continues to dominate the transport of the material through the conveying elements.

While ff_c and FR provide insights into the physicochemical properties of the material, the dimensionless Frd describes the material's behavior with respect to compressibility, which becomes particularly relevant for the screw geometry and their rotation speed. This parameter can be expressed as:

$$Frd = \frac{v_{FED}}{\sqrt{C_i g H}} \quad (16)$$

where g is the gravitational acceleration constant. Similar to the previous parameters, two material flow regimes can be distinguished based on the Frd . When the Frd is less than 1, gravitational forces dominate, and material movement is primarily governed by compression. In contrast, when the Frd exceeds 1, inertial forces dominate, allowing the material to resist movement against gravitational and compressive effects. According to Equation (16), the Frd depends on two parameters: the mass flow rate and the compressibility index (Carr index). [Fig. 2](#) illustrates the variation of the Frd with mass flow rate for different Carr index values. For pure Kollidon VA 64 (Carr index ≈ 0.15), achieving Frd higher than 1 requires an increase in the material's mass flow rate through the feeder. Conversely, reducing the Carr index, for instance, by using a polymer with lower compressibility value, enhances flowability and consequently increases the Frd .

Based on these results we found that, for effective feeding into the extruder, the ff_c should ideally be greater than 4, with no strict upper limit under favorable cohesive conditions. In contrast, the FR exhibits a narrower processing window, typically ranging from approximately 0.3 to 1. Regarding the Frd , a minimum value is recommended [48] to ensure adequate material movement during feeding (our geometry 0.3), while no definitive upper limit has been established under practical processing conditions.

Fig. 2. Frd as a function of mass flow rate in the feeder for different values of the compressibility index for polymer Kollidon VA64.

3.2. Dimensionless criteria inside the barrel of HME

During the extrusion process, material is conveyed through the extruder barrel by the combined action of mechanical and thermal forces, ultimately producing an extrudate for subsequent applications. The process begins in the feeder, where material is continuously introduced into the barrel at a constant feed rate. From there, it progresses under steady screw rotation through the feed, compression, and melt zones (see Fig. 3). These zones correspond to different temperature regimes necessary for processing the material. In the feed zone, the powder is transported along the conveying elements at ambient temperature. In the compression zone, the temperature increases toward the polymer's glass transition temperature, promoting powder mixing and partial compression. In the melt zone, the material is subjected to temperatures exceeding its melting point, ensuring homogeneous mixing before it is extruded through the die.

During extrusion, three primary limitations were identified, each of which must be tuned in relation to the geometry of the selected HME:

- Maximum feed rate capacity.** At fixed screw speed, when exceeding the throughput capacity of the screw configuration causes material accumulation in the hopper. This overflow, resulting from limited screw transport capability, is illustrated in Fig. 4. Such accumulation can lead to unsteady feeding, fluctuations in extrudate quality, and potential process interruptions.
- Minimum screw rotation required for proper barrel filling.** At lower screw speeds (below 50 RPM for our extruder geometry), the screws were unable to effectively convey and homogenize the material. This resulted in localized accumulation, particularly in the two mixing zones (see Fig. 3), where the material reached the maximum fill level. Such accumulation indicates insufficient axial and radial mixing, leading to incomplete melting and elevated pressure. When this expanded material volume exceeded the local barrel capacity, the torque demand on the screws surpassed the equipment's operational limits.
- Maximum screw rotation speed for effective material handling.** At high screw speeds (around 800 RPM for our extruder geometry), even under low feed rates, it was observed that the powder failed to engage properly with the screw elements and instead slipped along the screw flights without effective conveyance into the barrel. This phenomenon, known as starved feeding or powder slippage, occurs when screw rotation is too rapid for the powder to maintain sufficient frictional contact with the screws. Under these conditions, dominant forces acting on the powder, including gravitational, normal, and wall friction (Janssen effect) are inadequate to counteract centrifugal effects, leading to poor powder transport and underfeeding of the extruder barrel. This limitation places an upper boundary on the useable screw speed for powder-based formulations

Fig. 3. Material filling levels within the axial length of the extruder based on the geometry of the screw [49].

Fig. 4. Example of limitations imposed by the geometry of the selected HME system for the polymer Kollidon VA 64. The dashed lines with black scatter points illustrate the theoretical maximum feed rate of the screw as a function of screw geometry and rotation speed. The minimum screw speed is set at 50 RPM, while the maximum screw speed is set at 800 RPM. The percentage of the feeder volume represents different feeding states and capacities.

and is particularly relevant for low bulk density or poorly flowing materials.

Polymers are unique materials capable of exhibiting both pseudo-Newtonian and non-Newtonian behavior, depending on applied shear rates and temperature. Under these conditions, polymers may exist in five distinct states within the extrusion process: solid, elastic-plastic, viscoelastic, viscous, and glassy. Each state can be characterized by specific dimensionless criteria derived from the material's rheological properties. When combined with knowledge of the HME equipment geometry, this information provides detailed insight into the material's behavior within each temperature zone, as discussed in subsequent sections. To keep the description focused, this work presents primarily the behavior of the pure polymer Kollidon VA 64. However, the discussion section will further address the behavior of mixtures of this polymer with four different APIs to explore extrusion challenges and extrudability considerations.

3.2.1. Elastic-plastic state

Heating the polymer leads to its transition from a powder state into an elastic-plastic deformation region. This transition can be achieved by adjusting process parameters such as temperature or speed flow. As shown in Fig. 5A, measuring both storage modulus (G') and loss modulus

Fig. 5. (A) Demonstration of temperature oscillation sweep measurement for heating and cooling cycle, where Loss modulus (G'') and Storage modulus (G') as a function of temperature. Loss factor value is demonstrated in the [Supplementary Information Figure SI 10A](#). (B) Master curve of the temperature superposition for the reference temperature 130 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, where reduces modulus are function of the reduced angular frequency value. Value of the shift factors are shown in [Supplementary Information Figure SI 10B](#).

(G'') as functions of temperature allows determination of the polymer's glass transition temperature (T_g) and melting point (T_m), typically observed at the intersection or crossover of these two curves. In Fig. 5B, the behavior of the material is depicted across three distinct regions: the powder state combined with elastic-plastic deformation (Region I), the viscoelastic region (Region II), and the viscous region (Region III).

In Region I, the polymer begins transitioning from its solid powder state as increasing temperature or shear induces molecular mobility. Under such conditions, the thermal energy disrupts these ordered structures, the polymer becomes more plastic and elastic, displaying initial of viscoelastic behavior. To characterize such material property transition when temperature is below the glass transition temperature, we can define the dimensionless Bingham number (Bn):

$$Bn = \frac{\tau_p H}{\eta^* v_{EXT}} \quad (17)$$

where τ_p is the powder shear stress of the viscoelastic material, and η^* is the complex dynamic viscosity (reflecting both elastic and viscous contributions). Both these parameters are function of screw speed and temperature across the polymer's processing range. In Region I, where the molecular arrangement of the polymer remains relatively constant over a range of temperatures, variations in the Bn primarily arise from changes in screw speed and mass flow.

The Bn represents the combined contribution of parameters obtained from rheological measurements and HME operating conditions. The required screw speed is primarily governed by the material's rheological properties, particularly the powder shear stress and complex dynamic viscosity (see [Supplementary Information Figure SI 11](#)). The flow velocity in the extruder is obtained from Eq. (14) and is inversely proportional to the mean residence time of the material within the barrel. Consequently, the mass flow rate is directly proportional to the extruder flow velocity (v_{EXT}) (see [Supplementary Information Figure SI 12](#)). In addition, the gap between the screw shaft and flight ($H = 0.004$ m in the present study) defines the screw channel geometry, influencing the material's shear and pressure distribution during extrusion.

When the Bn is significantly greater than 1, the polymer's flow behavior is dominated by its powder shear stress, causing it to behave more like a solid. Under such conditions, substantial stresses are required to initiate flow, and effective transport is possible only at high screw speeds, as indicated by the red triangle in Fig. 6. Conversely, when the Bn is much less than 1, the powder shear stress has little influence, and the polymer behaves more like a fluid, with viscous forces dominating the flow. It should be noted that under these conditions, the

Fig. 6. Bn as a function of mass flow of the feeder and screw speed of the extruder (Eq. (17)). The green region demonstrates the working area based on the geometry of the extruder (discussed in Section 3.2).

material may still exist in powder, agglomerated, or granulated forms and can exhibit elastic characteristics during processing.

To ensure effective transport of the polymer along the screw, the Bn should remain within the operational green region, as illustrated in Fig. 6. The ideal working range for Bn lies slightly above 1 but should not exceed 30. Within this range, the polymer exhibits elastic-plastic behavior, which enhances material conveyance through the transport zones and reduces the torque demand on the extruder. Based on the obtained Bn values, it is possible to estimate appropriate screw rotation speeds relative to the mass flow rate. However, excessively high Bn values drastically narrow the processing window, ultimately making extrusion unfeasible with the same screw geometry.

3.2.2. Viscoelastic state (elastic deformation)

While the polymer is effectively transported through the conveying zones, its rheological behavior in the first kneading zone should ideally transition toward that of a viscoelastic material to enable efficient mixing and compression while maintaining a stable torque profile. In this stage, the polymer undergoes significant structural reorganization,

transforming from a relatively ordered to a more disordered bulk structure. This viscoelastic behavior corresponds to Region II in Fig. 5B, where the temperature lies between the glass transition temperature and the melting point. Within this disordered regime, energy dissipation occurs through both stress relaxation and creep compliance, as the material exhibits simultaneous elastic (solid-like) and viscous (fluid-like) responses. Because both mechanisms are active, it becomes difficult to determine which contribution dominates. To describe this transitional behavior quantitatively, the relaxation time is introduced, representing the characteristic time required for the polymer to relax internal stresses after deformation, essentially describing how quickly the material recovers its equilibrium configuration under given conditions.

Since polymers often consist of a broad distribution of molecular weights, their relaxation behavior cannot be described by a single relaxation time. Instead, a relaxation time spectrum is more appropriate, as illustrated in Fig. 7. As shown, relaxation time is highly dependent on processing temperature. At lower temperatures, the polymer behaves predominantly as an elastic material, exhibiting high relaxation times due to limited molecular mobility. In contrast, at elevated temperatures, the relaxation times shift toward lower values, reflecting behavior closer to that of an ideal viscous fluid. The spectrum of relaxation times is an intrinsic property of the polymer and can be experimentally estimated from rheological measurements using the generalized Maxwell model approximation.

During extrusion, the polymer resides within each screw element for a finite duration, defined as the characteristic process time (t_{pro}) which corresponds to the residence time per screw element. For estimation purposes, the screw can be divided into discrete elements, consisting of one conveying section or by four kneading elements, each having an identical wet volume of approximately 0.8 cm^3 (pycnometer measurement). Consequently, the entire screw can be modeled as 40 sequential elements, each approximated as an ideal continuous stirred-tank reactor (CSTR) arranged in series along the barrel. Considering the total free barrel volume (35.86 cm^3), each element handles approximately 0.9 cm^3 of material on average. In parallel, the material filling level per element, determined experimentally and illustrated in Fig. 3, is incorporated into this analysis. The final effective volume per element was further adjusted by a factor of two to account for the geometric scalability between the element length (2.2 cm) and diameter (1.1 cm). This correction ensures consistency when comparing different extruder

geometries. By combining the relaxation time obtained from rheological characterization with the characteristic process time determined for each extruder element, the dimensionless Deborah number (De) can be expressed as [50]:

$$De = \frac{\lambda}{t_{pro}} \quad (18)$$

In ideal macroscopic flow systems, $De \approx 1$ corresponds to the regime where both elastic and viscous effects are significant, and the material exhibits pronounced viscoelastic behavior. However, the boundary conditions of this criterion are not straightforward, as true coexistence of elastic and viscous responses rarely occurs in practice. It can only be stated that for ideal liquid systems, $De \rightarrow 0$, where viscous forces dominate, whereas for ideal solid or powder-like systems, $De \rightarrow \infty$, where elastic forces prevail [51].

As demonstrated above, the De reflects the local viscoelastic behavior of the material over the characteristic process time corresponding to a single element of the extruder. However, in polymer extrusion, it is equally important to understand the material's behavior on a global scale. To address this, another dimensionless parameter, the Weissenberg number (Wi), is introduced. This number characterizes the material response based on shear deformation rather than on process time. Unlike the De , the Wi directly depends on the processing conditions, such as screw speed and shear rate, and can therefore be effectively used for process scaling and for comparing different screw or barrel geometries. For a defined shear rate within the barrel [52], the Wi is expressed as:

$$Wi = \lambda \dot{\gamma} \quad (19)$$

While both criteria describe similar aspects of the process, the extremes of the Wi correspond closely to those of the De . When $Wi \rightarrow 0$, the flow is dominated by viscous forces, indicating liquid-like behavior. Conversely, when $Wi \rightarrow \infty$, elastic forces dominate, the material exhibits solid-like behavior.

To illustrate the evolution of both dimensionless parameters, the De and the Wi were plotted along the axial length of the screw, normalized by the total length ($L/D = 40$) (Fig. 8A and B). Each step on the plots corresponds to an individual screw element, where the relaxation time is obtained from rheological measurements, while the characteristic process time and shear rate are determined experimentally from the extrusion process. As shown in both figures, at the beginning of the extruder, the material behaves as a solid-like powder, where the relaxation time is relatively high. Under these conditions, the polymer cannot respond within the imposed processing time or deformation rate, resulting in $De \rightarrow \infty$ and $Wi \rightarrow \infty$. As the barrel temperature increases to approximately $90 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the relaxation time decreases, indicating that the polymer begins to lose its elastic dominance and becomes more processable. In this region, corresponding to the first kneading zone, the material still exhibits partial elastic recovery, which promotes homogeneous mixing. This regime is highlighted as the first blue region in both figures. When the temperature further increases beyond the glass transition temperature and approaches the melting point, both De and Wi decrease, marking the transition to a more liquid-like state, where viscous forces increasingly influence the flow behavior. In this regime, the polymer deforms readily and flows more easily through the screw elements, as indicated by the second blue region in Fig. 8A and B. Once the temperature exceeds the melting point, the relaxation time decreases sharply, and the polymer behaves as a disordered viscous melt. Here, flow is governed primarily by viscous dissipation rather than elastic recovery. This fully molten regime corresponds to the third blue region in Fig. 8A and B. In a hypothetical scenario where the temperature continues to rise, the material would approach an ideal Newtonian melt, where $De \rightarrow 0$ and $Wi \rightarrow 0$. It should be noted, however, that this “viscous-dominated” region only reflects the relative dominance of viscous over elastic forces, rather than a complete absence of elasticity. The detailed flow behavior of the polymer in this regime is further discussed in

Fig. 7. Weighted relaxation time spectrum. Each differential spectrum was derived by transforming experimental storage and loss modulus data into the spectrum of the relaxation time using Equations (8) and (9), as illustrated in the inset figure.

Fig. 8. Behavior of the dimensionless criteria along the axial length of the screw. The left y-axis represents the temperature profile of the barrel, while the right y-axis represents: (A) the De , determined at a mass flow rate of 9.05 g min^{-1} , and (B) the Wi , evaluated at a screw rotation speed of 300 RPM. The blue regions represent the achievable range of both parameters for the polymer Kollidon VA 64.

Section 3.2.3.

As discussed previously, both dimensionless numbers capture the transition between distinct flow regimes, ranging from ideal viscous flow to highly elastic, powder-like behavior. To visualize the historical evolution of polymer behavior across these regimes, the Wi was plotted against the De to construct a Pipkin diagram [53], as illustrate in Fig. 9. When the relaxation time of the polymer is extremely high, typically when the material is below its glass transition temperature, the molecular chains are immobilized, and deformation cannot occur within the applied process time. Under these conditions, $De \approx 10^6 - \infty$ and $Wi \approx 10^4 - \infty$, indicating strong nonlinear elasticity and solid-like behavior dominated by interparticle contact and stored elastic energy. The polymer behaves as a brittle or granular solid, with negligible viscous flow and limited chain mobility. As the temperature increases toward glass transient point, molecular mobility begins to increase, and the material transitions into a nonlinear viscoelastic regime. In this region ($De \approx 10^4 - 10^6$ and $Wi \approx 10^2 - 10^4$), both elastic and viscous forces

play comparable roles. The polymer network partially relaxes under shear, enabling segmental motion while still storing some deformation energy. This mixed response is critical for energy dissipation and distributive mixing in the initial stages of extrusion. When the temperature rises above glass transient point and approaches the melting point, the material enters a LVR, characterized by progressive chain disentanglement and reduction in structural constraints. Hence $De \approx 300 - 10^4$ and $Wi \approx 10 - 100$, reflecting a dominance of viscous flow with a measurable elastic component. This state ensures smooth conveying and efficient melting along the screw while maintaining a degree of elasticity that stabilizes the pressure profile. At temperatures exceeding melting point, the polymer transforms into a quasi-Newtonian melt, where chain entanglements are largely relaxed, and deformation is accommodated almost entirely by viscous flow. The corresponding range ($De \approx 1 - 300$ and $Wi \approx 1 - 10$) represents a regime in which the material behaves as a highly processable melt with minimal elastic recovery. Finally, as the temperature continues to increase, the polymer approaches an ideal Newtonian flow regime ($De < 1$ and $Wi < 1$), where shear viscosity solely governs deformation, and the response becomes independent of shear history. In this state, the melt flows freely with negligible elastic memory, though excessive temperature may induce thermal degradation or molecular weight reduction. From a processing perspective, the first kneading zone should ideally operate within the nonlinear or LVR, where both viscous and elastic forces coexist. This balance promotes efficient mixing, homogeneous melting, and stable torque response, ensuring consistent material transport and preventing flow instabilities or pressure fluctuations during extrusion.

As demonstrated in Fig. 9, the temperature range represents a critical parameter in defining the operational zones of the material during extrusion, as it primarily governs the rheological behavior and phase state of the polymer. Temperature directly affects the relaxation time, thereby determining whether the material behaves in a solid-like, viscoelastic, or viscous manner. In addition to temperature, processing parameters also have a secondary but non-negligible influence. For instance, the mass flow rate, which enters into the definition of the De through the characteristic process time, and the screw rotation speed, which determines the Wi via the shear rate, can both shift the boundaries between flow regimes. Consequently, small variations in these parameters may alter the local stress and strain-rate fields along the screw, slightly modifying the effective processing window of the material.

The selected ranges of both the De and Wi numbers are critical for understanding material behavior during extrusion, yet these transitions are often underappreciated in the rheological community [54]. Under conditions where process time is the dominant factor (i.e., governed by mass flow rate), the De should be greater than 300 in the kneading zones, indicating that elastic forces dominate and promote effective mixing and

Fig. 9. Pipkin diagram [53] representing the influence of shear strain history on the rheological behavior of the polymer. The diagram is a two-dimensional projection of material response as a function of two dimensionless numbers: the De and the Wi . It illustrates the transition between different flow regimes, ranging from elastic to viscous behavior, based on the relative timescales of material relaxation and applied deformation. This framework enables classification of the flow behavior during processing, especially under varying shear conditions.

compression. Conversely, in the conveying zones, $De < 300$ is preferable, allowing the material to behave in a more fluid-like manner, ensuring smooth transport. In terms of shear deformation, where screw rotation speed primarily governs the process, the Wi must exceed 10 in the kneading zones to ensure sufficient elastic response and compression. On the other hand, $Wi < 10$ is favorable in the conveying zones to promote viscous flow and stable transport along the barrel. These critical thresholds help define optimal operational windows and can serve as valuable design criteria for optimizing extrusion geometries.

3.2.3. Viscous state

When the material is homogeneously mixed and compressed, it is subsequently conveyed to the higher-temperature zones of the extruder, where the polymer begins to melt and transitions from a viscoelastic to a viscous state. This transition corresponds to Region III, as illustrated in Fig. 5B, where the loss modulus exceeds the storage modulus across the entire range of angular frequencies. This dominance of viscous over elastic response signifies the onset of a fully developed melt flow. As the transition advances, both moduli progressively decrease with increasing temperature, reflecting a reduction in molecular entanglements and structural order, and thus an enhancement of viscous flow behavior. To achieve this state, the polymer must absorb sufficient thermal energy to overcome intermolecular interactions and disrupt any remaining ordered domains or crystalline regions. Consequently, this melting region typically occupies the longest portion of the screw, accounting for roughly half of its total length, where continuous heat transfer from the barrel and mechanical shear ensures complete melting and homogenization of the material. In this zone, the polymer exhibits increased molecular mobility due to efficient heat conduction and shear-induced flow. The second kneading zone is strategically positioned within this region to further promote mixing and dispersion, particularly in multi-component systems. At this stage, the polymer exists predominantly in a molten state, where viscous forces dominate over elastic ones, and the flow can be characterized using the Reynolds number (Re), which quantifies the relative contributions of inertial and viscous forces in the system, and is expressed as:

$$Re = \frac{\rho_M v_{EXT} H}{\eta^*} \quad (20)$$

where ρ_M is the melt density of polymer, η^* is the complex viscosity. The Re is a function of three main parameters: the local temperature, the mass flow rate of the extruder, and the screw rotation speed. The Re in this context incorporates contributions from both rheological and process-related parameters. The rheological response is characterized by

the complex viscosity, in which the real and imaginary components represent the viscous and elastic contributions of the material, respectively. Both components exhibit dependence on temperature and screw rotation speed, as revealed by the frequency-sweep measurements (see Supplementary Information, Figure SI 13). In parallel, extruder-specific parameters, such as the flow velocity of the polymer melt and the gap distance between the screw shaft and flight, also play an essential role in determining the overall flow behavior. Together, these parameters define the balance between inertial and viscous forces in the system, influencing the flow stability and energy dissipation characteristics during extrusion.

Fig. 10 presents a series of Re contour plots for a polymer melt at two processing temperatures: 130 °C and 160 °C, while in Supplementary Information Figure SI 14 demonstrates complete dataset for 130 °C, 140 °C, 150 °C, and 160 °C. The green-shaded regions indicate the feasible operating zones under each temperature condition. While the maximum screw speed is constrained by equipment limitations (as discussed in Section 3.2), the minimum screw speed is defined by the maximum melt viscosity that still allows stable extrusion processing on the Pharma 11 extruder. At 130 °C, the temperature is close to the polymer's melting point, and elastic forces remain dominant over viscous forces. Therefore, achieving a flow regime with viscous-dominated behavior requires higher shear deformation, which limits the feasible processing window to higher screw speeds, where sufficient shear stress can overcome the elastic resistance. As the temperature increases to 140 °C, the material gains enough thermal energy to fully melt, resulting in a transition toward viscous-dominated behavior. Consequently, the processing window expands to include lower screw speeds (see Supplementary Information Figure SI 14). At 150 °C and 160 °C, the polymer is well above its melting point, and viscosity continues to decrease. This results in an increase in the Re , indicating enhanced flowability and broader operational flexibility. The system becomes more stable, and throughput can be increased without compromising processability. It should be noted that increasing the processing temperature generally enhances the polymer's processability by reducing viscosity and improving melt flow. However, the upper temperature limit must be carefully controlled, as excessive thermal input can lead to polymer degradation.

3.2.4. Viscoelastic state (elastic recovery)

After melting, the polymer re-enters a viscoelastic state, characterized primarily by elastic recovery and the onset of melt expansion. This expansion behavior depends solely on the intrinsic properties of the polymer melt and can be quantified from rheological measurements

Fig. 10. Re as a function of feeder mass flow rate and extruder screw speed, illustrated as black lines. Each graph corresponds to a different processing temperature, as follows: 130 °C and 160 °C. The green-shaded regions indicate the operational window defined by the extruder geometry, as discussed in Section 3.2. All Re values shown in the graphs should be multiplied by 10^{-6} .

obtained using the frequency sweep protocol (see Section 2.3.2). As the polymer passes the melting zone and enters the cooling section of the extruder, its temperature gradually decreases. In this region, the molten polymer is compressed through a narrow die opening and subsequently expands upon exiting into ambient conditions. Proper control of this expansion process is crucial, if the melt swell is excessive or insufficient, it may cause filament instability, die drooling, or even extrusion failure. The parameter describing this phenomenon is known as the die swell criterion (B) [55]. According to Tanner's theory [56], the B can be approximated using a first-order engineering model, expressed as:

$$B = k \frac{\sigma_n}{\tau_m} \quad (21)$$

where k is a die geometry and material-dependent constant (typically $k \approx 1/2$), σ_n is the normal stress of the polymer inside the die, and τ_m is the melt shear stress at the die wall. The behavior of both parameters at different temperatures and screw speeds is illustrated in Supplementary Information Figure SI 15. Inside the die, the polymer melt flows through a narrow channel, which induces intense shear deformation. Due to its viscoelastic nature, the melt develops both shear and normal stresses. The die walls constrain radial deformation, thereby storing elastic energy in the form of normal stress. When the polymer exits the die and experiences a sudden pressure drop, this stored energy is released, leading to extrudate swelling.

Fig. 11 presents the behavior of the B as a function of screw speed across a range of processing temperatures. At low temperatures (approximately 110 °C), the viscosity is high, resulting in large normal stresses and correspondingly high swell values ($B > 10$). This condition reflects strong elastic recovery, which can lead to flow blockage or unstable filament formation, making it unsuitable for processing. At moderate temperatures (120 – 130 °C), the melt exhibits a balance between viscous and elastic forces, yielding realistic swell values ($B \approx 1 - 3$). This range is optimal for maintaining stable extrusion and ensuring consistent filament quality. At higher temperatures (above 140 °C), particularly at high screw speeds, the material undergoes sufficient stress relaxation within the die. Consequently, the B can drop below 1, indicating minimal elastic recovery. While this may enhance dimensional control, over-relaxation can lead to filament thinning or surface instabilities due to premature dissipation of elastic stresses.

Fig. 11. B as a function of screw speed for a range of processing temperatures. The green-shaded area indicates a suitable operational window for stable extrusion.

3.2.5. Glassy state

As the final state of the polymer is not solely governed by the extrusion process itself, but rather by the cooling dynamics that occur once the material exits the die, it primarily reflects the polymer's post-processing behavior. During cooling to room temperature, the polymer undergoes structural relaxation, densification, and potential recrystallization, processes that ultimately define its mechanical properties, molecular orientation, and solid-state morphology. Consequently, as the filament exits the extruder, it enters a regime where the material's fragility becomes a key descriptor of its thermal-mechanical response. This parameter, representing the sensitivity of the polymer's viscosity to temperature near the glass transition, is directly obtained from rheological measurements performed via the temperature oscillation sweep method (see Supplementary Information Figure SI 16).

This fragile behavior implies that the material exhibits a rapid increase in viscosity with decreasing temperature, resulting in substantial structural rearrangements. These changes are associated with an increase in the activation energy barrier (E_A), as described by the Arrhenius equation ($\eta = \eta_0 \exp(E_A/k_B T)$). As the material approaches its glass transition temperature, it enters a supercooled liquid state, followed by solidification. In this regime, the material continuously adjusts its internal structure in response to temperature fluctuations, and the viscosity behavior deviates from the simple Arrhenius law. This deviation is characterized by the fragility index (M) [57], defined as:

$$M = \frac{\partial(\log \eta^*)}{\partial\left(\frac{T_g}{T}\right)} \Big|_{T=T_g} \quad (22)$$

As demonstrated in Fig. 12, the M , extracted from the slope of the Angell plot near the glass transition temperature, characterizes the thermal sensitivity of a polymer's viscosity. For Kollidon VA 64, the calculated M is approximately 6.5, indicating low fragility and classifying it as a strong glass-forming polymer. Such materials typically exhibit limited molecular mobility near the glass transition, resulting in brittle filaments upon solidification due to the rapid loss of segmental motion. In contrast, polymers with a fragility index exceeding ~ 20 display more pronounced viscosity changes near the glass transition region. These are referred to as fragile glass formers and are generally

Fig. 12. Angell plot [58] showing the temperature dependence of viscosity, where the x-axis represents the inverse temperature scaled by the glass transition temperature, and the y-axis shows the corresponding viscosity at each scaled temperature. The M is defined as the slope of the curve in the region near T_g value.

associated with greater molecular flexibility, leading to filaments with enhanced softness and mechanical resilience after cooling. Although the M is primarily an intrinsic property derived from rheological behavior, it provides a useful predictive parameter for assessing the post-processing performance of extruded materials, such as during milling, pelletizing, or spherization.

Even though the M reflects the viscoelastic response of a polymer in the supercooled melt state and captures its thermal transition dynamics, it does not directly describe the polymer's mechanical behavior in the solid state. The brittleness of the filament is not solely governed by fragility. Rather, it is influenced by a combination of molecular and structural factors. These include the flexibility of the polymer backbone, the degree of crystallinity, the extent of intermolecular hydrogen bonding, chain entanglement density, and the presence of plasticizers or additives. Each of these parameters significantly affects the final mechanical performance and toughness of the extrudate. Therefore, while the Angell plot provides valuable insight into the thermal and dynamic characteristics of the polymer melt, it should be complemented by mechanical characterization, such as tensile, flexural, or impact testing, to comprehensively assess filament brittleness and mechanical robustness.

3.3. Generation of extrusion map

Dimensionless criteria serve as valuable tools to evaluate the processability of a material under specific conditions. However, the key challenge lies in understanding how the material behaves across all processing zones simultaneously. To address this, we introduce the concept of an extrusion processability map, which integrates material behavior across different temperature zones of the extruder. The goal of this mapping approach is to identify potential weak points during processing and guide the decisions regarding modification of the formulation, extruder geometry, or adjust process parameters. By visualizing these interdependencies, the extrusion map provides a comprehensive overview of the material's performance along the entire extrusion path. It is important to note that, within the limits of simplifications considered during definition of above-mentioned dimensionless groups, constructed map provides a first-order approximation of process feasibility and highlights areas where further optimization or adaptation may be necessary.

One possible illustration of this concept is presented in Fig. 13, where eight dimensionless criteria are plotted on a radar chart. Each criterion corresponds to a distinct physical state of the polymer, ranging from powder → elastic-plastic → viscoelastic → viscous → glassy—arranged in clockwise direction starting from the 12 o'clock position. Adjacent to each criterion, the relevant process parameters influencing its behavior during extrusion are indicated in brackets. The dashed red lines represent the minimum threshold values necessary for successful extrusion, while black crosses denote the maximum values recorded during experimental analysis. The shaded region, in this case corresponding to the pure polymer Kollidon VA 64, falls entirely within the defined operational windows, highlighting the material's excellent processability under the selected extrusion parameters and temperature ranges. A summary of these parameters is provided in Table 1. This radar chart effectively integrates multiple dimensionless criteria, allowing for a comprehensive assessment of polymer behavior throughout the extrusion process. By simultaneously visualizing both critical thresholds and experimental outcomes, the extrusion map serves as a valuable predictive tool for evaluating material suitability, minimizing trial-and-error experimentation, and guiding process optimization for broader materials processing applications.

4. Discussions

As material passes through the HME process, it undergoes several physical states, each corresponding to specific zones within the extruder. These zones can be characterized using dimensionless numbers, which

Fig. 13. Example of extrusion map for polymer Kollidon VA 64.

Table 1

Summary of key processing parameters for the polymer Kollidon VA 64 during HME using the Pharma 11 extruder, with screw geometry illustrated in Fig. 3.

Parameter	Value
m /(g/min)	9.05
n /(RPM)	300
$T_{zone 1}$ /(°C)	60
$T_{zone 2}$ /(°C)	90
$T_{zone 3}$ /(°C)	110
$T_{zones 4-7}$ /(°C)	150
SME/(kJ kg⁻¹)	8678

reflect the material's behavior under defined temperature and screw speed conditions. Each dimensionless number is characterized by an optimal range, bounded by minimum and sometimes with maximum thresholds, indicating the suitable processing window. These criteria offer significant insights into the extrusion process, enabling predictive modeling with minimal experimental input.

In the **powder state**, the material experiences heterogeneous shear deformation, which intensifies with increasing shear rate. However, at low shear rates, the deformation may reach a limit where the material can no longer relax, making it resistant to further processing. In this initial zone, the physicochemical properties of the material dominate and are best described by three key dimensionless parameters: ffc , FR , and Frd . These parameters are crucial for predicting issues like bridging or arching in the feeder, as indicated by a low ffc . Additionally, cohesive or adhesive tendencies of the material can lead to poor screw engagement at high screw speeds, resulting in elevated axial pressure gradients, increased torque demands, and potential risk of mechanical overload. This information is especially critical for feeder design, where maintaining a stable feeding rate is essential to avoid fluctuations in extrusion throughput and ensure consistent material processing.

Within the internal zones of the extruder, one of the most critical material behaviors is observed in the **elastic-plastic state**, where the

material displays a balance between flow resistance and deformability. In this regime, the material exhibits a yield stress, meaning it resists flow until a critical shear force is applied. Although the influence of physicochemical properties is relatively minimal in this state, the initial powder compactness can significantly enhance pressure buildup, potentially leading to mechanical failure or clogging of the extrusion system. Understanding this behavior is essential when determining the placement and design of compression zones within the extruder, as this directly affects torque requirements during the onset of material flow. To overcome the challenges associated with yield-limited flow, barrel heating is often employed to transition the material into a **viscoelastic state**. In this phase, the material exhibits both elastic recovery and flow behavior, depending on residence time in the heated zone and local temperature fluctuations. These behaviors are highly sensitive to strain rate and thermal conditions, which are best characterized by dimensionless parameters such as the Wi and the De . Rather than simply indicating whether the material is elastic or viscous, these parameters describe its time-dependent deformation response relative to the screw speed and mass flow rate. By evaluating these criteria, it becomes possible to predict the material's performance in different screw configurations and to optimize the geometry and positioning of kneading and conveying elements. This predictive capability supports more efficient extruder design and enhances process control during HME operations.

When viscous forces dominate over elastic responses, the polymer behaves as a pseudo-Newtonian, shear-thinning fluid. In this **viscous regime**, the material is effectively transported as a melt with minimal pressure build-up, facilitating smooth filament extrusion and reducing elastic recoil. This state is advantageous for achieving dimensional consistency and continuous throughput. However, processing temperature plays a critical role in this regime. Excessively high temperatures can reduce the melt viscosity too much, leading to unstable strand formation, poor shape retention, and undesirable post-extrusion mixing. Conversely, lower temperatures may overly increase viscosity, narrowing the processability window, especially in geometrically constrained extruder zones. In typical polymer extrusion processes, a Re far below 1 confirms the dominance of viscous forces and laminar flow, characteristic of thermoplastic melts. Control over flow in this regime is primarily governed by temperature, mass flow rate, and screw speed. Nonetheless, modifying the physicochemical composition of the mixture, through additives, fillers, or plasticizers, introduces an additional degree of freedom to fine-tune the viscous behavior of the material. This capability is especially valuable for optimizing performance in targeted extruder geometries or for sensitive compounds.

Upon exiting the die, the polymer enters a critical phase transition from the melt to the solid state, where its **glassy behavior** plays a key role in defining the final shape and mechanical stability of the extrudate. One important descriptor of this stage is the B , which reflects the elastic energy stored in the polymer melt during flow through the die. This swelling behavior is a consequence of molecular orientation and stretching, and is governed by the material's ability to relax before exiting the die. Limited relaxation leads to higher die swell due to residual elastic memory, which can result in shape instability, dimensional inconsistencies, and compromised mechanical strength of the extrudate. Furthermore, B analysis can also be used to predict common extrusion defects such as dripping, die drool, or irregular strand expansion, all of which affect continuous material withdrawal and overall process stability. As the polymer cools below its glass transition temperature, molecular mobility decreases significantly. In this solidified regime, the M becomes a critical parameter to evaluate the brittleness of the final product. A low M implies a sharp drop in molecular mobility near glass transition point, often resulting in brittle behavior, reduced processability, and increased susceptibility to mechanical failure (e.g., screw jamming, die blockage, or cracking during handling). Importantly, the M also serves as a predictive indicator of the lower thermal processing boundary for a given polymer, helping to define the minimum

operational temperature at which sufficient molecular mobility is maintained to enable successful extrusion without structural degradation. Furthermore, the M can be employed as a predictive tool for assessing subsequent filament processability in powder form.

Based on the descriptions and analyses provided in the previous sections, extrusion maps were constructed for binary mixtures consisting of a polymer matrix and various APIs. These maps serve to demonstrate the processability of multicomponent systems under various extrusion conditions. A comprehensive summary of the results is presented in [Table 2](#), where all eight dimensionless criteria, alongside the SME , are listed. This table illustrates several examples where a polymer was blended with four different APIs: RIV, CBD, CBG, and CBN. These case studies demonstrate how variations in formulation can influence dimensionless criteria and, consequently, the processability of the material (SME value). The dimensionless criteria were optimized by adjusting key processing parameters to achieve an optimal extrusion performance.

It should be noted that the dimensionless numbers discussed in this study are not defined by fixed minimum or maximum thresholds. Instead, maintaining them within an optimal operational interval is crucial for achieving stable and continuous extrusion. In certain cases, these dimensionless criteria can even predict whether extrusion or feeding is feasible, particularly in the case of multicomponent powder mixtures. To illustrate this, a binary mixture was prepared by combining the polymer with an API over a specific compositional range to evaluate its flowability in the powder state. In multicomponent systems, the overall flowability tends to decrease, as evidenced by a notable reduction in the ffc . As shown in [Fig. 14A](#), blends containing 10 wt% of CBG exhibited a decrease in ffc to approximately 6.5, indicating a transition to cohesive flow behavior. This result highlights that even small additions of poorly flowing components can dominate the bulk flow characteristics of the mixture. These findings emphasize that, during HME of Kollidon VA 64 formulations, the presence of APIs with poor flowability significantly influences material handling and can determine critical process parameters, particularly in the feeding and conveying zones at room temperature.

When the FR is plotted against the Frd , as shown in [Fig. 14B](#), it becomes possible to simultaneously evaluate the material's cohesive and compressibility characteristics. Interestingly, when the polymer is blended with different APIs in binary mixtures, the observed trends deviate somewhat from those derived from the ffc (see [Fig. 14A](#)). This observation indicates that even materials with relatively high flowability, such as CBN, may still exhibit an enhanced adhesion tendency to the extruder walls. Such adhesion can lead to localized material accumulation within specific regions of the extrusion system, which may compromise process stability and, ultimately, product quality. However, in the case of CBG, where the material exhibits high cohesiveness combined with good compressibility, granulation can easily occur even within the feeder, as illustrated in the inserted picture in [Fig. 14B](#).

In the following section, three case studies are presented to demonstrate how process parameters influence the dimensionless numbers and how they can be correctly interpreted, as summarized in [Table 2](#).

4.1. Case study: RIV

The first case study examines RIV, an API with a significantly higher melting point than the polymer matrix used in the binary mixture. Although RIV itself exhibits poor flowability as a pure material, its incorporation into the polymer matrix markedly reduces the overall flowability of the powder blend comparing pure polymer. At high API loadings, or when only pure API is present, the powder becomes non-flowable and tends to compact within the feeder, posing serious handling and feeding challenges. Furthermore, the presence of RIV increases the internal elastic resistance of the blend, requiring higher screw speeds to initiate material movement. At the same time, the API decreases the relaxation time of the material, as indicated by a lower Wi ,

Table 2

Dimensionless numbers for multicomponent systems used to evaluate extrusion processability. Each label corresponds to the pure additive component, while the numerical value indicates its percentage in the blend, the remaining fraction is composed of the base polymer Kollidon VA 64. All key processing parameters selected for extrusion are provided in [Supplementary Information Table SI 1](#).

Sample	ff_c	FR	Frd	Bn	Wi	$Re \times 10^{-6}$	B	M	$SME \text{ kJ kg}^{-1}$
Kollidon VA 64	14.90	0.78	0.65	1.22	82.88	8.25	2.03	6.45	19.20
10 RIV	12.85	0.67	0.38	1.64	251.73	14.00	0.36	10.20	45.65
30 RIV	5.61	0.62	0.15	2.35	14.95	3.54	0.80	11.40	34.18
RIV	1.66	0.60	0.14	-	-	-	-	-	-
10 CBD	8.26	0.78	0.50	1.30	307.72	21.1	0.75	8.96	25.66
30 CBD	3.21	0.96	0.23	1.59	221.82	1.42	0.07	7.63	30.85
CBD	1.85	1.09	0.17	-	-	-	-	-	-
10 CBG	5.60	0.56	0.74	1.96	188.31	3.57	0.24	7.54	38.02
30 CBG	1.86	0.44	0.20	1.26	193.83	14.30	0.31	11.20	35.33
CBG	0.90	2.00	0.04	-	-	-	-	17.56	-
10 CBN	15.20	0.71	0.56	1.24	226.24	30.9	0.56	6.92	16.21
30 CBN	11.00	0.75	0.70	1.31	141.05	7.50	0.06	12.57	9.54
CBN	10.20	0.42	0.65	1.17	6.03	179.00	2.31	-	1.78

Fig. 14. (A) ff_c of the binary mixture of polymer Kollidon VA 64 and four APIs. (B) Comparative diagram of dimensionless numbers, showing the FR and the Frd for mixture of the polymer Kollidon VA 64 and four APIs. The picture demonstrates the behavior of pure CBG, which remains as a not flowing powder, whereas during mixing it begins to undergo granulation.

which paradoxically reduces the SME number despite the increased resistance to flow. Due to its high melting point, RIV exhibits limited meltability under typical processing temperatures, reflected by lower Re values. This implies a more elastic-dominated behavior with restricted viscous flow. The B remains below unity, indicating a greater propensity for die dripping rather than expansion at the die exit. Therefore, a higher cooling rate is beneficial to stabilize the extrudate and maintain filament integrity. In total, the incorporation of RIV approximately doubles the SME required for extrusion compared to the neat polymer, underscoring its significant influence on processability. Despite its rigidity in the solid state, RIV can act as a functional plasticizer under certain thermo-mechanical conditions by modifying the rheological and mechanical behavior of the polymer matrix. This effect is evidenced by the higher M compared to the pure polymer.

4.2. Case studies: CBD and CBG

The second and third case studies involve APIs CBD and CBG, both of which exhibit lower melting points than the polymer matrix. Despite their relatively low melting temperatures, both APIs demonstrate poor powder flowability, with pure CBD showing slightly better flow characteristics than pure CBG. When blended with the polymer, both CBD and CBG significantly reduce the flowability of the binary mixture and increase its compressibility, leading to poor feeding behavior, particularly at higher API concentrations. Similar to RIV, both CBD and CBG show low powder mobility, making the extrusion of the pure API com-

ponents impractical. Interestingly, the Bn remains comparable to that of the pure polymer matrix even as API content increases, suggesting that the material can still be conveyed under relatively low screw speeds. In both cases, the Wi is sufficiently high to indicate dominance of elastic forces in the early kneading zones, which is reflected in the elevated SME values compared to the pure polymer. For CBD, increasing API content leads to a decrease in Re , indicating stronger elastic behavior and reduced melt flow. In contrast, CBG shows the opposite trend, higher API concentrations lead to increased Re , suggesting improved melting and flow in the conveying zones due to better thermal softening. Both APIs exhibit B significantly below unity, implying a tendency for die dripping and low elastic recoil upon exiting the die. This necessitates the application of a higher cooling rate to enhance extrudate stability and promote desirable filament expansion. Interestingly, the presence of CBG increases the M , making the final extrudate more flexible but reducing its suitability for post-processing operations such as milling. In contrast, when CBD is incorporated, the M remains comparable to that of the pure polymer.

4.3. Case study: CBN

In the fourth case study, CBN possesses a melting point lower than that of the polymer matrix and exhibits good flowability in its pure form. In this scenario, the addition of CBN does not negatively affect the flowability of the binary mixture. In fact, continuous feeding of pure CBN without any polymeric additive is feasible. Similar to previously

discussed materials, CBN displays low internal elastic resistance, suggesting a wide operational window for screw speed during extrusion. Interestingly, at low concentrations, CBN significantly increases the elastic response of the binary mixture, as indicated by a higher Wi . However, with increasing API content, the Wi declines, reflecting a transition toward more viscous dominant behavior. The pure CBN component behaves nearly as a Newtonian fluid, with minimal elastic deformation resistance. As the concentration of CBN increases, the Re also rises substantially, indicating enhanced viscous flow behavior within the melt region of the extruder. Despite this, the B remains below unity, implying a tendency toward filament contraction and the need for increased cooling rates to stabilize the extrudate. Conversely, when extruding pure CBN without the polymer, the B increases significantly, leading to pronounced expansion upon die exit and improved filament formation. Overall, the addition of CBN strongly enhances the mechanical properties of the mixture and drives a transition from an elastic-dominated to a viscous-like flow regime. As a result, the SME required for processing decreases markedly with increasing CBN content, highlighting the improved processability of CBN rich formulations. The M of the material increases, making it comparable to that of formulations containing CBG or RIV.

It is important to note that direct comparison of dimensionless criteria and SME values across binary mixtures is constrained by differing key processing parameters (as summarized in [Supplementary Information Table SI 1](#)). These include variations in screw speed, temperature profile, and feed rate, which influence the observed processability behavior.

The case studies presented herein demonstrate the practical utility of rheological analysis as a predictive tool for assessing and optimizing the processability of multicomponent systems in HME. By translating rheological parameters into dimensionless criteria and correlating them with extrusion behavior, this framework enables the identification of optimal processing windows and highlights conditions that may lead to process instability or failure, such as die swell, melt fracture, or feeding issues. This methodology reduces reliance on empirical trial-and-error approaches by allowing targeted manipulation of key processing variables (e.g., temperature, screw speed, and formulation composition) and monitoring their direct influence on flow and energy input. Notably, optimization guided by rheological insights contributes to a reduction in SME , indicating improved energy efficiency of the extrusion process. Beyond HME, this process analytical framework could be extended to other continuous manufacturing technologies where viscoelastic and flow behaviors are critical, such as injection molding or additive manufacturing.

Importantly, the case studies highlight the distinct impact of each API on processability. RIV, with its high melting point and poor intrinsic flowability, substantially reduces powder mobility and increases the SME required for extrusion, presenting handling and feeding challenges. CBD and CBG, despite lower melting points, increase powder compressibility and reduce flowability, with CBG additionally prone to granulation within the feeder due to its cohesive nature. In contrast, CBN maintains good powder flowability and promotes a transition toward viscous-dominated melt behavior, reducing SME and improving extrudability. These trends, captured by the dimensionless criteria, demonstrate the predictive power of the framework, enabling identification of optimal processing windows, anticipation of flow instabilities, and informed adjustment of screw speed, temperature, and cooling strategies for each formulation. Thus, the integration of rheological characterization into process design holds promise for advancing formulation development, process robustness, and scalability feasibility in pharmaceutical and polymer engineering applications.

5. Conclusions

This study introduces a novel framework for evaluating and predicting the extrusion behavior of polymers and multicomponent mix-

tures by employing dimensionless criteria. By constructing extrusion maps based on critical parameters such as the Frd , Bn , Wi , Re , and B , we demonstrate how polymer behavior transitions through various states such as powder, elastic-plastic, viscoelastic, viscous, and glassy within the extruder. Each state is linked to distinct process challenges and performance indicators, providing a comprehensive understanding of material-process interactions. The developed dimensionless framework enables first-order predictions of extrudability, minimizing the need for extensive trial-and-error experimentation based solely on rheological measurements. Furthermore, it offers valuable insights for screw design, barrel temperature profiling, and formulation development. These insights are particularly significant for optimizing process efficiency, reducing material waste, and enhancing sustainability in pharmaceutical and broader polymer-processing industries. Ultimately, the proposed extrusion mapping approach lays a foundation for smarter, data-driven design of HME processes, with potential for adaptation across various material systems and industrial sectors.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Dan Trunov: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Lukáš Berčík:** Validation, Investigation. **Samuel Křiška:** Validation, Investigation. **Albert Behner:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Miroslav Šoós:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Resources, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtadv.2026.100734>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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